

**ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ПЛАТФОРМЫ WORDWALL КАК СРЕДСТВО
РАЗВИТИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОГО ИНТЕРЕСА ШКОЛЬНИКОВ В
ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ**

**THE USE OF THE WORDWALL PLATFORM AS A MEANS OF
DEVELOPING THE COGNITIVE INTEREST OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN
THE LEARNING PROCESS**

НАСОНОВА МАРГАРИТА СЕРГЕЕВНА,

Белгородский государственный национальный исследовательский университет.

ЖУРБА ЕЛИЗАВЕТА ПЕТРОВНА,

Белгородский государственный национальный исследовательский университет.

NASONOVA MARGARITA SERGEEVNA,

Belgorod State National Research University,

ZHURBA ELIZAVETA PETROVNA,

Belgorod State National Research University.

*Научный руководитель: Прокopenко Юлия Александровна,
доцент,*

Белгородский государственный национальный исследовательский университет.

*Scientific supervisor: Prokopenko Yulia Aleksandrovna,
Associate Professor,
Belgorod State National Research University.*

В данной статье рассматриваются особенности использования платформы Wordwall как средства развития познавательного интереса школьников в процессе обучения. Определены содержательные компоненты познавательного интереса. Охарактеризована сущность творческого поиска педагогов, направленного на использование в этих целях единства учебной и внеучебной деятельности учащихся. В результате проведенного исследования обоснована необходимость обогащения образовательного процесса интересным контентом, новейшими методами, приемами и формой работы, примером которых является программа Wordwall.

This article discusses the features of using the Wordwall platform as a means of developing the cognitive interest of schoolchildren in the learning process. The content components of cognitive interest are determined. The essence of the creative search of teachers aimed at using the unity of educational and extra-curricular activities of students for these purposes is characterized. As a result of the conducted research, the need to enrich the educational process with interesting content, the latest methods, techniques and forms of work, an example of which is the Wordwall program, is substantiated.

Ключевые слова: *образовательный стандарт, познавательный интерес, информационные технологии, программа Wordwall.*

Key words: *educational standard, cognitive interest, information technology, program Wordwall.*

Modern society is constantly being updated and puts a person in front of a lot of problems that he needs to solve. This requires continuous self-development through fundamental education, constant improvement of one's creative thinking, and the need for this must be embedded in a person as early as possible. As you know, such an activity as cognition begins to be carried out to a greater extent by a child upon entering school, where he gradually moves away from playing activities and begins to study. However, if once the school was able to transfer ready-made knowledge, skills and abilities to children, then with the entry into the stage of the information society, the transfer of knowledge in its entirety to children has become problematic. In this regard, since 2009, the Federal State Educational Standard of the second Generation has been operating in the Russian Federation, which is based on a system-activity approach, its task is to implement the "readiness for self-development and continuous education" of students. That is, at the moment, education is aimed at teaching schoolchildren to learn. In this regard, the question arises: how can an educational institution solve the task assigned to it.

In psychology and pedagogy, one of the key concepts is considered – cognitive interest, on which the entire learning process should be based in order to achieve the set goals. In pedagogical activity, many works and studies are devoted specifically to cognitive interest. S.L. Rubinstein defined it as "a special selective tendency of a person to the process of cognition, the nature of which is expressed in any particular area" [1]. The role of this phenomenon in educational activity was investigated by N.G. Morozova:

- interests are an assistant in order to effectively consolidate knowledge, skills, and abilities;
- increase the effectiveness of mental activity, which, as a result, is reflected in the overall level of personality development;
- have an effective influence on the formation of creative thinking, various skills and abilities;
- they become the reason for the improvement of the emotional state and the basis for the favorable course of all mental processes [2].

If we combine all of the above, we will get that cognitive interest will be interpreted as a selective orientation of the personality, directed to the field of knowledge, to its subject side and the very process of mastering knowledge, according to the definition of G.I. Shchukina [3].

It should be understood that cognitive interest is a phenomenon that has a complex structure. G.I. Shchukina explained it as follows:

- 1) The intellectual component is responsible for the readiness to study the object, its characteristics, important and essential features.
- 2) The emotional component includes positive emotions in the process of gaining knowledge.
- 3) The volitional component is the centralization of mental activity and efforts aimed at achieving the set goal [3].

The development of the cognitive process should take place according to the laws of age psychology. When children first come to school, they find themselves in new conditions that force them to switch from "free" play activities to work on assignment. During this period, the student is waiting for a new one, but his desire for it will gradually decrease if repetition after the teacher dominates in educational activities. Therefore, already at the initial stage of education and further, it is necessary to place the child in a situation where he can show independence and creativity, and this is possible only if there are cognitive interests.

However, cognitive interest does not manifest itself in a person from birth, but arises in the process of activity and its development in the process of schooling is an obvious necessity. Conditionally, within the framework of a theoretical review, the following stages of the formation of cognitive interest are distinguished [4]:

1. Curiosity as such is not a guarantee of the further development of aspirations for knowledge, as it is caused by external influences: for example, a teacher who brings interesting facts, visibility, and the like to the studied material. That is, the main role at this stage is played by entertainment as one of the properties of the pedagogical process. At the same time, it is important to understand that it is curiosity that has the opportunity to become the beginning of the path for the development of the desire for knowledge.

2. Curiosity manifests itself as a child's desire to delve into the essence of concepts and phenomena, without limiting himself to visual representations. At this stage, it is not enough to "occupy" the student, you need to allow him to carry out independent creative and search activities. The emotional and volitional component is already activated here: the student has a range of positive emotions from his own discoveries achieved through his own activities.

3. The stage of cognitive interest is characterized by the emergence of cognitive motives: here the student receives little information from the teacher and textbooks, he has a desire to learn new things for his own mental enrichment. At this stage, the foundation for further self-education is being formed.

4. At the stage of theoretical interest, all the information accumulated by the child is transformed into a tool for practical activity.

Teachers have considered and tested in practice many different methods and tools for the formation of cognitive interest. There are several main options: to begin with, the development of motivation to learn through the content of educational material. Here you can apply the surprise factor, i.e. tell or show new and entertaining facts and phenomena; link theory with practice; include a historical aspect in the presented material, since often the motive for studying this topic is more understandable and close to students within the framework of its historical development; to highlight current scientific achievements that have been made thanks to materials available from school textbooks.

It cannot be denied that not all students can be occupied with the help of a single educational material. It is also possible to consider the formation of cognitive interest through a special organization of the educational process. Here we can talk about the use of gaming technologies, since they bring new impressions to the process against the background of daily educational activities; about setting a problem for students, for which they need to make their own plan to solve it. A particularly effective way to stimulate cognitive interest in the age of information technology is the use of information and communication technologies. The introduction of ICT in the learning process makes it possible to link educational activities with computer technologies familiar to schoolchildren. Moreover, this shows the child that a computer can be not only an element of the entertainment sphere, but also a useful part for discovering new knowledge.

One of the programs that will help the teacher to increase cognitive interest in his lesson is the Wordwall program. Wordwall is a versatile multifunctional platform that serves to create interactive and printed materials. The program has a Russian-language version, which cannot but please its users. Thanks to the simple interface, the teacher can easily create exercises using images and texts in it, suitable for both an interactive whiteboard when working in the classroom and for online classes with distance learning for schoolchildren [5].

The online tool is suitable for teachers of different disciplines, as this service includes a constructor of 18 types of tasks for practicing grammar, vocabulary, knowledge of natural science subjects, mathematics and others. It is possible to create games such as "match up" (match words with their explanations), "quiz" (quiz), "unjumble" (fix jumbled words in a sentence), "Gameshow quiz" (quiz, where there is a bonus round, and extra lives), "random wheel" (game-roulette), "Crosswords" (crosswords) and much more [5].

During the training, students perform interesting and diverse tasks, the results of which are recorded in a summary table, where the teacher can track the student's progress and see gaps in

knowledge. The advantage of this service is that after creating any type of task, it can be converted to another one by making the necessary changes. This function contributes to the formation of creative thinking among students and a departure from the template solution of the same type of tasks. All types of exercises that the teacher creates are saved in the personal account.

In order to explore the possibilities of developing cognitive activity of schoolchildren using the Wardwall online platform, we conducted a survey on the basis of OGBOU Secondary School No. 4 in Valuyki, Belgorod region. The survey was attended by students of the 7th grade consisting of 30 people.

To complete the questionnaire, each student had to indicate their favorite subject, the reason for their interest in the chosen subject and what kind of teaching tools the teacher uses in the classroom. After analyzing the questionnaires, we received the following results.

Pic. 1 shows the students' answer to the question "Which subject is of the greatest interest to you?"

Pic. 1. Percentage ratio of students' interest in individual subjects

The greatest interest among students is a math lesson (57%), Russian language is considered less interesting by 7th grade students – 23%, computer science – 12%, literature is interesting only 8% of students. In our opinion, this result is related to the teacher's ability to interest children.

Next, we asked the question "Why are you interested in the subject you have chosen?" The most frequent responses from students are shown in Pic. 2.

Pic. 2. The reason for the interest in the chosen subject

According to the survey, most students like the way the teacher explains the material, which means that the teacher uses all possible methods to increase cognitive interest in the lesson. 24% of students are fascinated by the subject itself and 19% of students describe their interest in the subject with ease of assimilation of the material. To the question "What means does the teacher use when explaining the material in your chosen lesson?" The children gave the following answers (Pic. 3).

Pic. 3. Teaching tools used by the teacher in explaining the material

Analysis of the graph data shows that using the Wordwall platform in a math lesson allows you to make fixing any topic interesting and effective, as well as increase cognitive interest. Also, the most interesting lessons, according to the students, are those in which the teacher equally uses interactive methods of explaining the material and handouts. Lessons in which the teacher uses only a textbook and handout to explain the topic are less interesting and contribute less to the formation of cognitive interest.

At the end of the survey, we found out from the students the level of their motivation to study the subject, depending on the chosen digital means of teaching the teacher. Thus, a low level of motivation is characterized by a child's unwillingness to study school discipline, an average level of motivation can be described as a neutral attitude to learning, regardless of the chosen means of learning, a high level of motivation indicates that the student is interested in the classroom and the use of a digital service increases his cognitive interest. The survey results are shown in Pic. 4.

Pic. 4. The level of motivation of students to study the subject

According to the survey, the majority of students (53%) are highly motivated to learn and are interested in gaining knowledge, 30% of students are neutral about the educational material and 17% of students do not show interest in the subject.

Thus, our research allows us to conclude that with the introduction of the Federal State Educational Standard, the use of various information methods of explanation, along with traditional ones, is an integral part of the educational process. No matter how difficult and boring the lesson topic may be, it will become interesting to the student if the educational material on the screen is presented in colors, with sound and other effects, and fixing the topic will be in the form of interesting tasks that can be easily done in the online Wordwall constructor.

The use of information technology in the classroom can transform the learning process, making it more effective and attractive for students. Learning using information technology becomes a creative search for a child, from which you can get satisfaction and through which you can assert yourself.

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